

Effects of newly synthesized creatine derivatives on memory, motor coordination, and depressive-like behavior in mice

Ivalina Valchinkova¹

¹ Department of Pharmacology, Pharmacotherapy and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Ivanka Kostadinova (i.kostadinova@pharmfac.mu-sofia.bg)

Received 30 May 2026 ♦ Accepted 11 June 2026 ♦ Published 30 June 2026

Citation: Valchinkova I, Kostadinova I (2026) Effects of newly synthesized creatine derivatives on memory, motor coordination, and depressive-like behavior in mice. *Pharmacia* 73: e201921. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e201921>

Abstract

This study investigated the effects of creatine monohydrate (CrM, 1.5 g/kg/day); newly synthesized creatine lysinate (CrLys), creatine leucinate (CrLeu), creatine isoleucinate (CrIsoleu), creatine arginate (CrArg), and creatine valinate (CrVal) at a dose of 5 g/kg/day; and the antidepressants citalopram and fluoxetine at a dose of 20 mg/kg in the passive avoidance test, rotarod test, and tail suspension test (TST). After 2 weeks of peroral administration in mice, an increase in latency time in the passive avoidance test was observed in the groups treated with CrLeu and fluoxetine. In the rotarod test, the group that received CrIsoleu reached better outcomes on day 14 compared to the other groups. A slight decrease in immobility time in the TST was observed in the groups treated with CrM, CrLys, and fluoxetine. Based on the current results, supplementation with CrM, CrLys, CrLeu, and CrIsoleu shows promise in improving physical and cognitive performance in mice.

Keywords

Creatine derivatives, mice, passive avoidance, rotarod, tail suspension test

Introduction

Creatine (*N*-aminoiminomethyl-*N*-methyl glycine) is a naturally occurring substance that is endogenously synthesized (~1 g/day) in the liver, kidneys, and pancreas from the amino acids glycine, methionine, and arginine (Dome et al. 2019). Creatine can also be obtained from the diet (~1 g/day), mainly from sources such as beef, pork, chicken, fish, human milk, or dietary supplements (Dome et al. 2019; Kreider and Stout 2021). Creatine is found in the human body mainly in free (60%–70%) and phosphorylated (30%–40%) forms. Most of the total body creatine is stored in skeletal muscle, and the remaining amount is found in cells with high metabolic activity, such as those of the heart, retina, brain, and testicles (Wyss and Kaddurah-Daouk 2000).

One of the main functions of creatine is to immediately supply energy to tissues with increased energy demands, such as muscles and brain. This can be achieved by the high-energy phosphate bonds of phosphocreatine (PCr), which are available for immediate adenosine triphosphate (ATP) replenishment under energy-demanding conditions (Persky and Brazeau 2001). Based on these characteristics, it has been widely used to improve performance during anaerobic exercise (Rawson and Volek 2003). In addition to muscles, neurons also need such an energy supply, as they carry out many processes that require energy (Klivenyi et al. 1999; Persky and Brazeau 2001; Rawson and Volek 2003). Supplementation can increase brain levels of creatine up to a threshold, beyond which the excess is excreted (Joncquel-Chevalier Curt et al. 2015).

Creatine is one of the most popular ergogenic aids for athletes and weightlifters seeking to improve their sport and exercise performance and mitigate recovery time. Studies reveal that creatine supplementation exerts positive ergogenic effects on single and multiple bouts of short-duration, high-intensity exercise activities, in addition to potentiating adaptations to exercise training. Creatine supplementation demonstrates the ability to enlarge the pool of intracellular creatine, leading to an increased cellular ability to resynthesize ATP. This leads to increases in maximal strength, maximal work output, power production, sprint performance, and fat-free mass. Additionally, creatine supplementation may speed up recovery time between bouts of intense exercise by mitigating muscle damage and promoting faster recovery (Wax et al. 2021).

The relationship between creatine and cognitive performance is suggested by genetic creatine disorders—L-arginine-glycine amidinotransferase (AGAT), guanidinoacetate-methyltransferase (GAMT), or a creatine transporter (SLC6A8) deficiency—characterized by mental dysfunction (global developmental delay or intellectual disability) (Wyss and Kaddurah-Daouk 2000; Joncquel-Chevalier Curt et al. 2015). Oral creatine supplementation largely reversed these dysfunctions in AGAT and GAMT deficiency but not in SLC6A8 deficiency (Braissant et al. 2011). Creatine is also thought to have a role in neuronal plasticity (Jost et al. 2002). Mental training has been demonstrated to elevate brain creatine levels, suggesting an upregulation of resting energy storage (Valenzuela et al. 2003). Higher resting creatine levels have been shown to improve performance in cognitive tasks such as recognition memory (Ferrier et al. 2000). Data from all these studies suggest putative cognitive benefits of creatine supplementation (Avgerinos et al. 2018).

Accumulated data from more than 40 years suggest that creatine metabolism and availability may have anti-depressive effects (Niklasson and Agren 1984; Agren and Niklasson 1988; Kato et al. 1992; Kato et al. 1994; Silveri et al. 2003; Kondo et al. 2016; Yoon et al. 2016). The data from these studies have led to increased interest in the assessment of the effects of creatine or creatine precursors that can affect brain phosphagen levels, markers of depression, and the therapeutic effect of antidepressant medications (Roitman et al. 2007; D'Anci et al. 2011; Smith et al. 2014). For example, the creatine precursor S-adenosyl-L-methionine (SAME) has been reported to be an effective treatment for clinical depression. Allen et al. (2010) reported that rats fed creatine diets (4%) for 5 weeks changed depression-like behavior in the forced swim test in a sex-dependent manner, with female rats exhibiting antidepressant-like behavior. There are data indicating that the combination of single creatine treatment and exercise promoted greater benefits in mice with chronic mild stress-induced depression than creatine or exercise separately (Ahn et al. 2016). Pazini et al. (2017) stated that creatine at 10 mg/kg, administered p.o. for 21 days, abolished corticosterone-induced depressive-like behaviors in mice. Leem et al. (2018) reported that mice exposed to mild chronic stress for 4 weeks had a greater effect on hippocampal neurogenesis when creatine and exercise were

combined compared with each treatment in chronic mild stress-induced depression. There are some data from human trials indicating that creatine supplementation may influence depression (Balestrino and Adriano 2019). Evaluation of the effects of creatine supplementation (6 g/day for 6 weeks) in bipolar patients showed increased remission rates in the creatine group vs. the placebo group. These authors reported that adjunctive creatine therapy (6 g/day for 6 weeks) in patients with bipolar depression improved verbal fluency tests (Toniolo et al. 2017).

There are plenty of data indicating that the benefits of creatine monohydrate supplementation go well beyond increasing muscle Cr and PCr levels and thereby enhancing high-intensity exercise and training adaptations. Creatine supplementation may support healthy glucose management; heart metabolism; and health, particularly during ischemic challenges; mental health and many other functions (Kreider and Stout 2021).

In this study, the effects of newly synthesized creatine derivatives on their potential to improve learning and memory, increase physical endurance, and influence behavioral depression were examined in the passive avoidance test, rotarod test, and tail suspension test in mice.

Materials and methods

Animals and treatment

Male albino mice, line H, with a body weight of 28–32 g, were divided into nine groups of six animals in each group ($n = 6$). Food and water were available *ad libitum*. During the whole experiment, the animals were maintained at room temperature (22 ± 3 °C), humidity of 30%, and a lighting schedule of a 12 h light/dark cycle. Experiments were performed during the light part of the cycle. Each group was placed in the laboratory 30 min before the start of the experiment. The animals were divided into the following groups depending on the administered substances and their doses:

- 1st group—control animals receiving only drinking water;
- 2nd group—animals receiving creatine monohydrate at a dose of 1.5 g/kg/day (CrM 1.5 g/kg/day);
- 3rd group—animals receiving creatine lysinate at a dose of 5 g/kg/day (CrLys 5 g/kg/day);
- 4th group—animals receiving creatine leucinate at a dose of 5 g/kg/day (CrLeu 5 g/kg/day);
- 5th group—animals receiving creatine arginate at a dose of 5 g/kg/day (CrArg 5 g/kg/day);
- 6th group—animals receiving creatine isoleucinate at a dose of 5 g/kg/day (CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day);
- 7th group—animals receiving creatine valinate at a dose of 5 g/kg/day (CrVal 5 g/kg/day);
- 8th group—animals receiving citalopram hydrobromide 20 mg/kg;
- 9th group—animals receiving fluoxetine hydrochloride 20 mg/kg.

Citalopram hydrobromide and fluoxetine hydrochloride were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA). Creatine derivatives were synthesized and provided by Prof. Lyubomir Vezenkov from the University of Chemical Technology and Metallurgy, Sofia, Bulgaria. Creatine derivatives were administered to the experimental animals for 2 weeks in drinking water, and citalopram and fluoxetine were administered via oral gavage. On days 1, 7, and 14, the passive avoidance test, rotarod test, and tail suspension test (TST) were performed. The experiment was conducted in accordance with Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes and approved by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (No. 415/17.12.2024).

Passive avoidance test

The learning and memory abilities of the experimental mice were evaluated by a passive avoidance test using an automated Gemini Avoidance System (San Diego Instruments). The apparatus consisted of two identical compartments (25 × 20 × 16 cm each) with an electrified grid floor. The chambers were separated by a wall with a guillotine door (8 × 6 cm). The test started with a 20 s acclimatization period. Each mouse underwent one trial with a maximum duration of 300 s. If a mouse entered the dark chamber, a weak electric shock with an intensity of 0.5 mA and a duration of 3 s was applied through the grid floor. Learning was evaluated by the latency of entry into the dark compartment. Increased latency time indicated better memory retention (Gevrenova et al. 2023).

Rotarod test

The rotarod test is used for the evaluation of motor function and fatigue levels in mice and rats and for the assessment of potential therapeutic approaches (Wang et al. 2021). The rotarod apparatus is composed of a rotating rod and vertical walls to separate mice into individual compartments, ensuring that they do not interfere with each other during testing. Mice were placed on the rod of the apparatus (Ugo Basile, Rota Rod 47 600) in an accelerating mode from 4 to 40 rpm (acceleration time 30 s), and the latency to fall was recorded (Kostadinova et al. 2023). Each animal fell onto levers located on the top of the base unit under the corresponding compartment, with the latency to fall automatically registered (Keane et al. 2024). Each animal was given three consecutive trials with a 15 min inter-trial interval and a maximum of 300 s per trial. The average time of the three consecutive trials was used for analysis (Luh et al. 2017).

Tail suspension test (TST)

The tail suspension test (TST) is used to evaluate antidepressant-like behavior in mice by measuring immobility when they are suspended by their tails (Can et al. 2012). In the present study, the tail suspension setup consisted of plastic enclosures (20 × 25 × 40 cm) (Kostadinova et al. 2023) separated by an opaque partition to eliminate external sensory

cues (Mann and Chesselet 2015). Two animals could be observed at the same time. Following the procedure of Castagné et al. (2009a), with minor modifications, each mouse was suspended by the tail 20 cm above the floor of the chamber using adhesive tape placed < 1 cm from the tip of the tail. The test session consisted of a single 6 min trial, in which the first 2 min served as habituation and the last 4 min were used to measure the immobility time (Valvassori et al. 2017). Immobility time was defined as hanging passively without attempts to reach the tail by bending the body (Mann and Chesselet 2015). The latency to first immobility was also recorded. In behavioral studies on mice, specifically the forced swim test and the TST, the latency to first immobility is the time, usually measured in seconds, that elapses from the start of the test until the first period without any escape behavior, such as struggling or climbing the tail. During this period, the mouse remains completely immobile for a specified period, often defined as at least 1–2 s.

Statistical analysis

Statistical processing and graphical presentation of the obtained results were completed with GraphPad Prism 6.0 software. The arithmetic means and the standard errors of the arithmetic mean (SEM) were determined for all data. A statistically significant difference between the compared means was checked using one-way ANOVA and Tukey's test. A *p*-value of 0.05 or lower between the groups was considered statistically significant.

Results

When examining the influence of creatine derivatives on learning and memory processes (Fig. 1), the most significant increase in latency was observed on day 14 in the groups treated with CrLeu ($p \leq 0.0001$) and fluoxetine ($p \leq 0.001$) compared to the control group. CrLeu significantly prolonged the latency compared to the groups treated with CrM, CrArg, and CrVal ($p \leq 0.0001$), as well as to the groups treated with CrIsoleu and citalopram ($p \leq 0.01$). On day 14, a statistically significant increase in latency was also observed in the group treated with CrLys ($p \leq 0.05$) compared to the control group. In the group treated with CrLeu 5 g/kg/day ($p \leq 0.01$) on day 14, a significant improvement in the memory of the experimental animals was observed compared to CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day. A similar improvement was observed on day 14 between CrLeu 5 g/kg/day ($p \leq 0.01$) and the group treated with citalopram 20 mg/kg.

In the rotarod test (Fig. 2), the results showed a significant increase in latency time between days 1 and 14 in the group treated with CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day ($p \leq 0.05$). In the last week, a statistically significant improvement in motor coordination was observed in the group that received CrIsoleu compared to the groups treated with CrLeu ($p \leq 0.01$), CrVal ($p \leq 0.001$), CrLys ($p \leq 0.0001$), fluoxetine ($p \leq 0.0001$), and the control group ($p \leq 0.001$).

The results of the TST (Fig. 3) showed that there was no statistically significant difference in immobility time, an

Figure 1. Effect of creatine derivatives on learning and memory in the passive avoidance test in mice. Results are presented as arithmetic mean \pm SEM. Statistically significant differences: * $p \leq 0.05$ —when comparing the control group and the group treated with CrLys 5 g/kg/day on day 14; ** $p \leq 0.01$ —between the group treated with CrLeu 5 g/kg/day and CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day on day 14; between CrLeu 5 g/kg/day and citalopram 20 mg/kg on day 14; *** $p \leq 0.001$ —between the control group and fluoxetine on day 14; **** $p \leq 0.0001$ —between the control group and CrLeu 5 g/kg/day on day 14; between CrM 1.5 g/kg/day and CrLeu 5 g/kg/day on day 14; between CrLeu 5 g/kg/day and CrArg 3 g/kg/day on day 14; between CrLeu 5 g/kg/day and CrVal 5 g/kg/day on day 14.

Figure 2. Effect of creatine derivatives on motor coordination in the rotarod test in mice. Results are presented as arithmetic mean \pm SEM. Statistically significant differences: * $p \leq 0.05$ —when comparing on day 7 between the groups treated with CrM 1.5 g/kg/day and CrLeu 5 g/kg/day and CrM 1.5 g/kg/day and CrVal 5 g/kg/day; # between day 1 and day 14 in the group receiving CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day; ** $p \leq 0.01$ —on day 7 in the group treated with CrM 1.5 g/kg/day and CrArg 5 g/kg/day; on day 14 between CrLeu 5 g/kg/day and CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day; *** $p \leq 0.001$ —on day 14 between the control group and CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day, as well as between CrVal and CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day; **** $p \leq 0.0001$ —on day 14 between CrLys 5 g/kg/day and CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day, as well as between CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day and fluoxetine.

Figure 3. Evaluation of the antidepressant effect of creatine derivatives in the TST. Results are presented as arithmetic mean \pm SEM.

Figure 4. Estimation of the latency time to the first period of immobility in the TST in mice treated with creatine derivatives. Results are presented as arithmetic mean \pm SEM. *** $p \leq 0.001$ —on day 1 between the control group and CrLeu 5 g/kg/day; **** $p \leq 0.0001$ —on day 1 between the control group and CrM 1.5 g/kg/day; on day 1 between the control group and CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day; on day 1 between the control group and citalopram 20 mg/kg.

indicator of an antidepressant effect, among the groups. A decrease in immobility time, especially on days 7 and 14, was observed in the groups treated with CrM, CrLys and fluoxetine.

Fig. 4 presents a comparison of the latency times to the first period of immobility in the TST in mice treated with creatine derivatives. A statistically significant increase in time to first immobility was observed only on day 1 of the experiment. The time to first immobility was significantly increased in the groups treated with CrM, CrLeu, CrIsoleu, and citalopram compared to the control group.

Discussion

In the present study, the effects of newly synthesized creatine derivatives after 2 weeks of administration were investigated in the passive avoidance test, rotarod test, and TST. The results obtained from the passive avoidance test showed a significant increase in latency time on day 14 in the groups treated with CrLeu and fluoxetine compared to the control group. CrLeu significantly prolonged the latency time on day 14 compared to the groups treated with CrM, CrArg, CrVal, CrIsoleu, and citalopram. On day 14, a statistically significant increase in latency was also observed in the group treated with CrLys compared to the control group. There is a wealth of data supporting the positive effects of creatine on attention, memory, and mental fatigue. Creatine supplementation has been shown to improve attention under short-term hypoxic conditions (Turner et al. 2015) and improve mood and psychomotor function in sleep-deprived subjects (McMorris et al. 2006). There are data on improvements in intelligence test scores and working memory (Rae et al. 2003) and reduced mental fatigue (Watanabe et al. 2002). The data suggest that creatine supplementation in humans increased brain pools of both creatine (Dechent et al. 1999) and the PCr/ATP ratio (Pan and Takahashi 2007) at doses that enhance cognition. All these data lead to the conclusion that creatine supplementation can have a positive impact on brain physiology and function in humans (Snow

et al. 2018). Avgerinos et al. (2018) suggested a potential benefit of oral creatine supplementation in different groups, such as healthy individuals, aging individuals, stressed individuals, and vegetarians, on short-term memory and intelligence, but for other cognitive aspects, no differences were observed. The authors concluded that individuals subjected to various types of stress and aging have more positive effects from creatine supplementation than young adults.

In the present study, the passive avoidance test was used, which is a fear-motivated, one-trial learning task used in rodents to assess memory (Kassa et al. 2015). The test is based on the natural preference of rodents for dark environments. They are trained to avoid a dark compartment after experiencing an unpleasant stimulus there (Ghafarimoghadam et al. 2022). The present investigation showed gradual improvement in memory processes for 2 weeks in the group treated with fluoxetine—an antidepressant belonging to the selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) class. To a lesser extent, this effect was also observed in the group treated with citalopram, which belongs to the same group of antidepressants. The study of Sakhaie et al. (2020) examined the effects of adolescent fluoxetine administration (5 mg/kg/day) on passive avoidance learning and memory in young adult male and female rats. The results of the study indicated that juvenile fluoxetine administration improves memory retention in the passive avoidance test in females. Sakhaie et al. (2020) stated that chronic fluoxetine treatment has sex-dependent effects on passive avoidance memory and brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) mRNA expression, but the pain threshold decreases in both sexes. The authors concluded that memory, pain sensitivity, and the BDNF level are influenced by the manipulation of the serotonergic system (Sakhaie et al. 2020). The amygdala, hippocampus, and prefrontal cortices, which contain a dense concentration of serotonin receptors, are involved in fear learning and memory processing. Therefore, the serotonergic system can be influenced pharmacologically by administering agonists and antagonists of serotonin receptors, as well as selective SSRIs, and these can have effects on emotional learning and memory (Bauer 2015).

There are data indicating that treatment with fluoxetine significantly improves memory performance in patients with major depressive episodes (Levkovitz et al. 2002) and improves memory impairments and decreased hippocampal cell proliferation induced by valproic acid in rats (Welbat et al. 2016). Although the findings on the effects of antidepressants on memory remain controversial, the differences may be related to the study model, type of animals, duration and dose of treatment, and different memory tests (Sakhaie et al. 2020).

In the rotarod test, the results showed a significant increase in latency time between days 1 and 14 in the group treated with CrIsoleu 5 g/kg/day. In the last week, a statistically significant improvement in motor coordination was observed in the group that received CrIsoleu compared to the groups treated with CrLeu, CrVal, CrLys, fluoxetine, and the control group. This effect may be related to the direct positive effects of leucine and isoleucine on muscle strength and recovery. The findings of Reule et al. (2017) showed that 12-week leucine-rich amino acid supplementation (L-leucine, L-valine, and L-isoleucine) can counteract the negative effects of eccentric exercise and reduce exercise-induced strength loss. The branched-chain amino acids (BCAAs), such as valine, leucine, and isoleucine, are essential amino acids. They are substrates and regulators of muscle protein synthesis. Evidence suggests that leucine, in particular, enhances protein synthesis through the mTOR signaling pathway, regulation of protein synthesis, and stimulation of insulin secretion (Reule et al. 2017; Holeček 2022).

The results of the TST showed that there was no statistically significant difference in immobility time, an indicator of an antidepressant effect, among the groups. A decrease in immobility time, especially on days 7 and 14, was observed in the groups treated with CrM, CrLys, and fluoxetine. The previous study confirmed these results, revealing a slight decrease in immobility time in the

groups treated with CrM 1.5 g/kg/day and CrLys 6 g/kg/day (Kostadinova et al. 2023).

The present study showed that the antidepressants citalopram and fluoxetine had different effects on immobility time in the TST. Oral administration of fluoxetine led to a gradual decrease in immobility within 2 weeks, indicating antidepressant-like behavior. In the group treated with citalopram, a gradual increase in immobility time was observed from the first to the second week. In contrast, the time to first immobility on day 1 in the group receiving citalopram was significantly prolonged compared to that in the group treated with fluoxetine. The groups treated with CrM, CrLeu, and CrIsoleu also showed a statistically significant increase in time to first immobility compared to the control group.

In the study of Castagné et al. (2009b), fluoxetine (32 and 64 mg/kg) weakly and dose-dependently decreased the duration of immobility in the forced swim test (FST) in NMRI mice, compared with vehicle controls. Its administration also dose-dependently increased the latency to the first immobility. The authors stated that, in C57BL/6/J mice, fluoxetine did not significantly affect the duration of immobility over the dose range of 16–64 mg/kg but significantly increased the latency to the first immobility at 32 mg/kg (Castagné et al. 2009b). The effects of the antidepressants—fluoxetine and citalopram—in different studies may vary due to the type of test (TST or FST), as well as the strain of the mice and the dose applied.

Acknowledgements

Acknowledgments are given to Prof. Lyubomir T. Vezenkov from the University of Chemical Technology and Metallurgy, Sofia, Bulgaria, for the synthesis and provision of the creatine derivatives and to the Medical University of Sofia for the financial support.

References

- Agren H, Niklasson F (1988) Creatinine and creatine in CSF: indices of brain energy metabolism in depression. Short note. *Journal of Neural Transmission* 74(1): 55–59. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01243575>
- Ahn NR, Leem YH, Kato M, Chang HK (2016) Effects of creatine monohydrate supplementation and exercise on depression-like behaviors and raphe 5-HT neurons in mice. *Journal of Exercise Nutrition & Biochemistry* 20(3): 24–31. <https://doi.org/10.20463/jenb.2016.09.20.3.4>
- Allen PJ, D'Anci KE, Kanarek RB, Renshaw PF (2010) Chronic creatine supplementation alters depression-like behavior in rodents in a sex-dependent manner. *Neuropsychopharmacology* [official publication of the American College of Neuropsychopharmacology] 35(2): 534–546. <https://doi.org/10.1038/npp.2009.160>
- Avgerinos KI, Spyrou N, Bougioukas KI, Kapogiannis D (2018) Effects of creatine supplementation on cognitive function of healthy individuals: A systematic review of randomized controlled trials. *Experimental Gerontology* 108: 166–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exger.2018.04.013>
- Balestrino M, Adriano E (2019) Beyond sports: Efficacy and safety of creatine supplementation in pathological or parapsychological conditions of brain and muscle. *Medicinal Research Reviews* 39(6): 2427–2459. <https://doi.org/10.1002/med.21590>
- Bauer EP (2015) Serotonin in fear conditioning processes. *Behavioural Brain Research* 277: 68–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbr.2014.07.028>
- Braissant O, Henry H, Béard E, Uldry J (2011) Creatine deficiency syndromes and the importance of creatine synthesis in the brain. *Amino Acids* 40(5): 1315–1324. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00726-011-0852-z>
- Can A, Dao DT, Terrillion CE, Piantadosi SC, Bhat S, Gould TD (2012) The tail suspension test. *Journal of Visualized Experiments* [JoVE] (59): e3769. <https://doi.org/10.3791/3769>
- Castagné V, Moser P, Porsolt RD (2009a) Behavioral assessment of antidepressant activity in rodents. In: Buccafusco JJ (Ed.) *Methods of Behavior Analysis in Neuroscience*. CRC Press/Taylor & Francis, Boca Raton, (FL), Chapter 6.
- Castagné V, Porsolt RD, Moser P (2009b) Use of latency to immobility improves detection of antidepressant-like activity in the behavioral despair test in the mouse. *European Journal of Pharmacology* 616(1–3): 128–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2009.06.018>

- D'Anci KE, Allen PJ, Kanarek RB (2011) A potential role for creatine in drug abuse? *Molecular Neurobiology* 44(2): 136–141. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12035-011-8176-2>
- Dechent P, Pouwels PJ, Wilken B, Hanefeld F, Frahm J (1999) Increase of total creatine in human brain after oral supplementation of creatine-monohydrate. *The American Journal of Physiology* 277(3): R698–R704. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpregu.1999.277.3.R698>
- Dome P, Tombor L, Lazary J, Gonda X, Rihmer Z (2019) Natural health products, dietary minerals and over-the-counter medications as add-on therapies to antidepressants in the treatment of major depressive disorder: a review. *Brain Research Bulletin* 146: 51–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainresbull.2018.12.015>
- Ferrier CH, Alarcón G, Glover A, Koutroumanidis M, Morris RG, Simmons A, Elwes RD, Cox T, Binnie CD, Polkey CE (2000) N-Acetyl aspartate and creatine levels measured by ¹H MRS relate to recognition memory. *Neurology* 55(12): 1874–1883. <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.55.12.1874>
- Govrenova R, Kostadinova I, Stefanova A, Balabanova V, Zengin G, Zheljeva-Dimitrova D, Momekov G (2023) Phytochemical Profiling, Antioxidant and Cognitive-Enhancing Effect of *Helichrysum italicum* ssp. *italicum* (Roth) G. Don (Asteraceae). *Plants (Basel, Switzerland)* 12(15): 2755. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12152755>
- Ghafari Moghadam M, Mashayekh R, Gholami M, Fereydani P, Shelley-Tremblay J, Kandezi N, Sabouri E, Motaghinejad M (2022) A review of behavioral methods for the evaluation of cognitive performance in animal models: Current techniques and links to human cognition. *Physiology & Behavior* 244: 113652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2021.113652>
- Holeček M (2022) Side effects of amino acid supplements. *Physiological Research* 71(1): 29–45. <https://doi.org/10.33549/physiolres.934790>
- Joncquel-Chevalier Curt M, Voicu PM, Fontaine M, Dessein AF, Porchet N, Mention-Mulliez K, Dobbelaere D, Soto-Ares G, Cheillan D, Vamecq J (2015) Creatine biosynthesis and transport in health and disease. *Biochimie* 119: 146–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biochi.2015.10.022>
- Jost CR, Van Der Zee CE, In 't Zandt HJ, Oerlemans F, Verheij M, Streijger F, Franssen J, Heerschap A, Cools AR, Wieringa B (2002) Creatine kinase B-driven energy transfer in the brain is important for habituation and spatial learning behaviour, mossy fibre field size and determination of seizure susceptibility. *The European Journal of Neuroscience* 15(10): 1692–1706. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1460-9568.2002.02001.x>
- Kassa J, Bajgar J, Kuca K, Jun D (2015) Behavioral Toxicity of Nerve Agents. In: Gupta RC (Ed.) *Handbook of Toxicology of Chemical Warfare Agents* (2nd Edn). Academic Press, Elsevier, San Diego, Chapter 35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-800159-2.00035-X>
- Kato T, Takahashi S, Shioiri T, Inubushi T (1992) Brain phosphorous metabolism in depressive disorders detected by phosphorus-31 magnetic resonance spectroscopy. *Journal of Affective Disorders* 26(4): 223–230. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0327\(92\)90099-R](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0327(92)90099-R)
- Kato T, Takahashi S, Shioiri T, Murashita J, Hamakawa H, Inubushi T (1994) Reduction of brain phosphocreatine in bipolar II disorder detected by phosphorus-31 magnetic resonance spectroscopy. *Journal of Affective Disorders* 31(2): 125–133. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0327\(94\)90116-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0327(94)90116-3)
- Keane SP, Chadman KK, Gomez AR, Hu W (2024) Pros and cons of narrow- versus wide-compartment rotarod apparatus: An experimental study in mice. *Behavioural Brain Research* 463: 114901. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbr.2024.114901>
- Klivenyi P, Ferrante RJ, Matthews RT, Bogdanov MB, Klein AM, Andreasen OA, Mueller G, Wermer M, Kaddurah-Daouk R, Beal MF (1999) Neuroprotective effects of creatine in a transgenic animal model of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Nature Medicine* 5(3): 347–350. <https://doi.org/10.1038/6568>
- Kondo DG, Forrest LN, Shi X, Sung YH, Hellem TL, Huber RS, Renshaw PF (2016) Creatine target engagement with brain bioenergetics: a dose-ranging phosphorus-31 magnetic resonance spectroscopy study of adolescent females with SSRI-resistant depression. *Amino Acids* 48(8): 1941–1954. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00726-016-2194-3>
- Kostadinova I, Danchev N, Landzhov B, Tsvetkova D, Marinov L, Ivanova I (2023) Creatine lysinate – part II: effects on the motor coordination and muscle hypertrophy in mice. *Pharmacica* 70(4): 967–972. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacica.70.e110718>
- Kreider RB, Stout JR (2021) Creatine in health and disease. *Nutrients* 13(2): 447. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13020447>
- Leem YH, Kato M, Chang H (2018) Regular exercise and creatine supplementation prevent chronic mild stress-induced decrease in hippocampal neurogenesis via Wnt/GSK3β/catenin pathway. *Journal of Exercise Nutrition & Biochemistry* 22(2): 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.20463/jenb.2018.0009>
- Levkovitz Y, Caftori R, Avital A, Richter-Levin G (2002) The SSRIs drug Fluoxetine, but not the noradrenergic tricyclic drug Desipramine, improves memory performance during acute major depression. *Brain Research Bulletin* 58(4): 345–350. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-9230\(01\)00780-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-9230(01)00780-8)
- Luh LM, Das I, Bertolotti A (2017) qMotor, a set of rules for sensitive, robust and quantitative measurement of motor performance in mice. *Nature Protocols* 12(7): 1451–1457. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2017.062>
- Mann A, Chesseelet MF (2015) Techniques for Motor Assessment in Rodents. In: LeDoux MS (Ed.) *Movement Disorders* (2nd Edn). Academic Press, Boston, 139–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-405195-9.00008-1>
- McMorris T, Harris RC, Swain J, Corbett J, Collard K, Dyson RJ, Dye L, Hodgson C, Draper N (2006) Effect of creatine supplementation and sleep deprivation, with mild exercise, on cognitive and psychomotor performance, mood state, and plasma concentrations of catecholamines and cortisol. *Psychopharmacology* 185(1): 93–103. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-005-0269-z>
- Niklasson F, Agren H (1984) Brain energy metabolism and blood-brain barrier permeability in depressive patients: analyses of creatine, creatinine, urate, and albumin in CSF and blood. *Biological Psychiatry* 19(8): 1183–1206.
- Pan JW, Takahashi K (2007) Cerebral energetic effects of creatine supplementation in humans. *American Journal of Physiology – Regulatory, Integrative and Comparative Physiology* 292(4): R1745–R1750. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpregu.00717.2006>
- Pazini FL, Cunha MP, Azevedo D, Rosa JM, Colla A, de Oliveira J, Ramos-Hryb AB, Brocardo PS, Gil-Mohapel J, Rodrigues ALS (2017) Creatine prevents corticosterone-induced reduction in hippocampal proliferation and differentiation: possible implication for its antidepressant effect. *Molecular Neurobiology* 54(8): 6245–6260. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12035-016-0148-0>
- Persky AM, Brazeau GA (2001) Clinical pharmacology of the dietary supplement creatine monohydrate. *Pharmacological Reviews* 53(2): 161–176. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-6997\(24\)01490-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-6997(24)01490-X)
- Rae C, Digney AL, McEwan SR, Bates TC (2003) Oral creatine monohydrate supplementation improves brain performance: a double-blind, placebo-controlled, cross-over trial. *Proceedings, Biological Sciences* 270(1529): 2147–2150. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2003.2492>
- Rawson ES, Volek JS (2003) Effects of creatine supplementation and resistance training on muscle strength and weightlifting performance.

- Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research 17(4): 822–831. [https://doi.org/10.1519/1533-4287\(2003\)017%3C0822:EOCSAR%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1519/1533-4287(2003)017%3C0822:EOCSAR%3E2.0.CO;2)
- Reule CA, Scholz C, Schoen C, Brown N, Siepelmeyer A, Alt WW (2017) Reduced muscular fatigue after a 12-week leucine-rich amino acid supplementation combined with moderate training in elderly: a randomised, placebo-controlled, double-blind trial. *BMJ Open Sport & Exercise Medicine* 2: e000156. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjsem-2016-000156>
- Roitman S, Green T, Osher Y, Karni N, Levine J (2007) Creatine monohydrate in resistant depression: a preliminary study. *Bipolar Disorders* 9(7): 754–758. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-5618.2007.00532.x>
- Sakhaie N, Sadegzadeh F, Dehghany R, Adak O, Hakimeh S (2020) Sex-dependent effects of chronic fluoxetine exposure during adolescence on passive avoidance memory, nociception, and prefrontal brain-derived neurotrophic factor mRNA expression. *Brain Research Bulletin* 162: 231–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainresbull.2020.06.009>
- Silveri MM, Parow AM, Villafuerte RA, Damico KE, Goren J, Stoll AL, Cohen BM, Renshaw PF (2003) S-adenosyl-L-methionine: effects on brain bioenergetic status and transverse relaxation time in healthy subjects. *Biological Psychiatry* 54(8): 833–839. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3223\(03\)00064-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3223(03)00064-7)
- Smith RN, Agharkar AS, Gonzales EB (2014) A review of creatine supplementation in age-related diseases: more than a supplement for athletes. *F1000Research* 3: 222. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.5218.1>
- Snow WM, Cadonic C, Cortes-Perez C, Roy Chowdhury SK, Djordjevic J, Thomson E, Bernstein MJ, Suh M, Fernyhough P, Albensi BC (2018) Chronic dietary creatine enhances hippocampal-dependent spatial memory, bioenergetics, and levels of plasticity-related proteins associated with NF- κ B. *Learning & Memory [Cold Spring Harbor, N.Y.]* 25(2): 54–66. <https://doi.org/10.1101/lm.046284.117>
- Toniolo RA, Fernandes FBF, Silva M, Dias RDS, Lafer B (2017) Cognitive effects of creatine monohydrate adjunctive therapy in patients with bipolar depression: Results from a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Journal of Affective Disorders* 224: 69–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2016.11.029>
- Turner CE, Byblow WD, Gant N (2015) Creatine supplementation enhances corticomotor excitability and cognitive performance during oxygen deprivation. *The Journal of Neuroscience [the official journal of the Society for Neuroscience]* 35(4): 1773–1780. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.3113-14.2015>
- Valenzuela MJ, Jones M, Wen W, Rae C, Graham S, Shnier R, Sachdev P (2003) Memory training alters hippocampal neurochemistry in healthy elderly. *Neuroreport* 14(10): 1333–1337. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.wnr.0000077548.91466.05>
- Valvassori SS, Varela RB, Quevedo J (2017) Animal models of mood disorders: Focus on bipolar disorder and depression. In: Conn M (Ed.) *Animal Models for the Study of Human Disease* (2nd Edn). Elsevier, Amsterdam, Netherlands, Chapter 38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809468-6.00038-3>
- Wang P, Wang D, Hu J, Tan BK, Zhang Y, Lin S (2021) Natural bioactive peptides to beat exercise-induced fatigue: A review. *Food Bioscience* 43: 101298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbio.2021.101298>
- Watanabe A, Kato N, Kato T (2002) Effects of creatine on mental fatigue and cerebral hemoglobin oxygenation. *Neuroscience Research* 42(4): 279–285. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-0102\(02\)00007-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-0102(02)00007-X)
- Wax B, Kerksick CM, Jagim AR, Mayo JJ, Lyons BC, Kreider RB (2021) Creatine for exercise and sports performance, with recovery considerations for healthy populations. *Nutrients* 13(6): 1915. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13061915>
- Welbat JU, Sangrich P, Sirichoat A, Chaisawang P, Chaijaroonkhanarak W, Prachaney P, Pannangrong W, Wigmore P (2016) Fluoxetine prevents the memory deficits and reduction in hippocampal cell proliferation caused by valproic acid. *Journal of Chemical Neuroanatomy* 78: 112–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchemneu.2016.09.003>
- Wyss M, Kaddurah-Daouk R (2000) Creatine and creatinine metabolism. *Physiological Reviews* 80(3): 1107–1213. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.2000.80.3.1107>
- Yoon S, Kim JE, Hwang J, Kim TS, Kang HJ, Namgung E, Ban S, Oh S, Yang J, Renshaw PF, Lyoo IK (2016) Effects of creatine monohydrate augmentation on brain metabolic and network outcome measures in women with major depressive disorder. *Biological Psychiatry* 80(6): 439–447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2015.11.027>

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: No 415/17.12.2024 Bulgarian Food Safety Agency.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

The investigations were conducted with financial support from the Young Researcher 2024, Project № D-106/29.05.2024, to the Council of Medical Science of the Medical University of Sofia, Bulgaria.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

I. Valchinkova <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3711-583X>

I. Kostadinova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7283-8983>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.